

Training of social education on prevention of the victim behavior

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Feb 12, 2024

Revised Nov 13, 2024

Accepted Nov 21, 2024

Keywords:

Adolescent victim behavior

Educational interventions

Professional development

Specialized training

Teacher competencies

ABSTRACT

This study focused on assessing the impact of a specialized training program in dealing with victim behavior among teenagers. A total of 200 social educators from Kazakhstan participated in the study, evenly divided into an experimental group, which underwent training, and a control group, which did not receive training. A 100-point test was used in the study to evaluate pre- and post-training assessments. The average score on the pre-tests in both groups was 43. After the training, a significant increase in scores was observed in the experimental group, averaging 75.74, indicating the effectiveness of the training. The control group showed a slight increase with an average post-test score of 48.73. Statistical analysis underscored the impact of the training. Paired sample t-test for the experimental group revealed a significant mean difference with a significant value ($p < 0.001$). The change in the control group was also significant but small ($p < 0.001$). Independent samples t-test between the group results after testing indicated that the success of the experimental group was significantly higher ($p < 0.001$). These results demonstrate the value of targeted training to enhance the capabilities of social educators in managing the behavior of victimized adolescents, emphasizing the need for such specialized programs in educational institutions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The conditions of adolescent development are complex and multifaceted, often marked by issues that can profoundly impact a young person's life. Among these issues is the inclination towards victim behavior—a phenomenon that is increasingly drawing attention in the field of social education. Such behavior, characterized by victimization either through circumstances or interpersonal relationships, can have long-term detrimental consequences for the psychological and emotional well-being of adolescents [1], [2]. The role of social educators in mitigating this trend is crucial since their intervention can redirect the trajectory of adolescents' lives toward more positive outcomes [3].

This article aims to investigate the hypothesis that training social educators in modern methods of working with adolescents can enhance their ability to prevent and address victim behavior in this age group. This study is grounded in the understanding that the adolescent period is crucial for the development of healthy self-esteem and resilience to adverse life experiences [4]. The hypothesis posits that well-prepared social educators can play a transformative role in the lives of adolescents prone to victim behavior.

Victim behavior among adolescents can manifest in various forms, including, among other things, bullying, cyberbullying, and social isolation [5]. The effects of such experiences are not merely transient; they often have far-reaching consequences for the mental health and social integration of the affected individuals. It is in this context that the role of social educators becomes paramount. They possess unique opportunities for identifying, intervening, and potentially eliminating harmful behavior patterns that adolescents may exhibit or experience [6], [7]. Therefore, the training of social educators becomes a matter of urgent importance. Modern educational methodologies and psychological knowledge offer educators a plethora of resources. These methods are diverse and encompass a range of approaches, from direct intervention strategies to the development of school-wide programs aimed at creating a safe and inclusive environment for all students [8], [9].

The current educational environment constitutes a unique set of challenges and opportunities for social educators working with adolescents. The increasing complexity of social dynamics, fueled by technological progress and changing cultural norms, has created a need for more nuanced and adaptive approaches to education [10], [11]. Social educators are at the forefront of this evolution, tasked with guiding adolescents through a key stage of their development. Therefore, the training of these educators must be comprehensive, dynamic, and reflective of the current social context [12], [13]. One of the key components of effective education is an emphasis on understanding adolescent psychology. The adolescent period is characterized by rapid physical, emotional, and cognitive changes [14]. Social educators must possess a deep understanding of these developmental processes to effectively address the challenges faced by adolescents. This includes an awareness of typical issues within this age group, such as identity formation, peer pressure, and the struggle for autonomy [15]. In addition to understanding adolescent development, social educators should also be trained in specific intervention strategies to address victim behavior problems. These strategies may involve counseling methods, conflict resolution skills, and techniques to enhance resilience and self-esteem in adolescents [5]. Educators should also be able to recognize signs of victimization, which can often be subtle or hidden. Early identification and intervention are crucial for preventing the escalation of victim behavior and its long-term consequences [15].

Another important aspect of education is the creation of a favorable and inclusive school environment. Social educators play a key role in shaping the school culture. They should be trained to implement policies and practices that promote respect, empathy, and kindness among students [16]. This includes anti-bullying programs, peer support systems, and initiatives that celebrate diversity and inclusivity. A positive school culture can significantly reduce the frequency of victim behavior and provide a safe space for the development of all students [17]. Furthermore, training should also encompass strategies for interacting with parents and the community at large. The role of family and society in shaping adolescent behavior cannot be overestimated. Social educators need skills to engage with families and collaborate with the community to effectively address broader issues impacting the lives of adolescents [18]. This may involve working with parents to understand their child's needs, collaborating with community organizations to provide additional support, and advocating for policies that protect adolescents and expand their opportunities [19], [20].

Thus, the training of future social educators in preventing adolescents' inclination toward victim behavior is a multifaceted task. This requires a profound understanding of adolescent development, specific intervention strategies, the creation of a conducive school environment, and interaction with families and communities. By addressing these areas, social educators can better equip themselves to guide adolescents away from victim behavior toward a more positive and fulfilling developmental trajectory.

Significant research efforts delve into the psychological aspects of adolescent victim behavior, emphasizing the long-term impact of early life experiences. Studies in this field underscore the correlation between adverse childhood experiences and the development of victim behavior in subsequent years, highlighting the acute need for early intervention strategies in social education [19], [21]. Further research explores the interplay between self-esteem, peer relationships, and victim behavior, identifying low self-esteem and poor peer relationships as significant predictors [10], [12]. The influence of the school environment on adolescent behavior is another crucial theme. Research in this area indicates that schools fostering an inclusive and supportive culture witness fewer instances of bullying and victimization [19], [21], [22]. This is corroborated by studies advocating for the implementation of comprehensive anti-bullying programs as an effective preventive measure against victim behavior in schools [23].

The effectiveness of various intervention strategies employed by social pedagogues is thoroughly investigated. An analysis of counseling methods shows that approaches aimed at fostering resilience and self-confidence skills in adolescents are particularly effective [24], [25]. Additionally, the literature underscores the importance of restorative practices in schools, emphasizing their role in cultivating empathy and reconciliation among students [15], [18]. Training and professional development for social pedagogues are also crucial areas of focus. Reviews in this field point to a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical

application in the training of social pedagogues, urging the expansion of experiential learning opportunities to bridge this gap [1]. It is emphasized that continuous professional development is necessary for social pedagogues to adapt to the changing needs of adolescents [6], [26].

The impact of digital media on adolescent behavior is an evolving area of research. Studies in this field explore the influence of social networks on adolescents' self-perception and peer behavior, highlighting the necessity of incorporating digital literacy into the training of social pedagogues [8]. This aspect becomes increasingly relevant in the era of digital technologies, where online interaction significantly shapes the social experience of adolescents [16]. In conclusion, the literature presents a rich spectrum of research on adolescent victim behavior and the role of social education. It covers various aspects, ranging from psychological factors and the school environment to intervention strategies and professional development, all contributing to a deeper understanding of how best to prepare social pedagogues for their pivotal role.

In the context of Kazakhstan, this article plays a crucial role in addressing the need for enhancing the qualifications of future social pedagogues, especially in the field of preventing adolescent victim behavior, which is relevant for the entire post-Soviet space [1]. The emphasis on modern methodologies and intervention strategies provides a vital resource for educators in Kazakhstan who may encounter unique challenges in meeting the social and emotional needs of adolescents within the cultural, economic, and educational framework of the country. The education system in Kazakhstan, like in many other countries, is constantly evolving to meet the complex demands of modern society. This involves addressing issues such as bullying, peer pressure, and other forms of victim behavior that can significantly impact the development of adolescents [14]. The article sheds light on these issues and proposes comprehensive strategies to equip educators with the necessary tools and knowledge.

Additionally, the article emphasizes the necessity of continuous professional development and training for social pedagogues. In a country like Kazakhstan, where traditional and modern values often intersect, social pedagogues must be adept at addressing these complexities and applying their knowledge in a manner that is both culturally sensitive and effective. In conclusion, the article addresses the paramount task of enhancing the potential of social pedagogues in Kazakhstan in identifying, intervening, and preventing victim behavior among adolescents. In doing so, it contributes to the broader goal of creating a healthier, more favorable, and inclusive environment for the younger generation in Kazakhstan.

This article addresses a pertinent issue in the field of social education: the need to enhance the capabilities of social pedagogues in preventing and correcting victim behavior among adolescents [18]. Despite existing training programs, there remains a gap in equipping educators with modern methods specifically designed to address the intricate dynamics of adolescent victim behavior [5]. This gap underscores the necessity for additional targeted training for social pedagogues.

The primary aim of this research is to investigate whether additional training in modern methodologies can significantly enhance the effectiveness of social pedagogues in this domain. The research's objective is to provide empirical data to support or refute the hypothesis that such training can positively impact educators' capabilities in identifying, intervening, and preventing victim behavior among adolescents. By accomplishing these objectives, the article aims to contribute significant ideas and practical recommendations to the field of social education, with a specific focus on enhancing the preparation and effectiveness of educators in Kazakhstan and potentially in other similar educational contexts. The specific objectives of this article are: i) develop a comprehensive training program that encompasses modern methodologies and cutting-edge practices in addressing the victim behavior of adolescents; ii) implement this training program with a selected group of social pedagogues and assess its effectiveness compared to traditional teaching methods where victim behavior is not the main focus; and iii) evaluate the effectiveness of the developed program in comparison to a control group without intervention.

2. METHOD

The initial step involved the development of an instructional program that integrated modern methodologies and cutting-edge practices in addressing the victim behavior of adolescents. This program was formulated based on a review of contemporary literature in this field, consultations with experts, and an analysis of successful intervention strategies utilized in various educational contexts. The program is presented in Table 1.

This study employed comprehensive methodologies to assess the effectiveness of the program "modern methods of social pedagogues' work with adolescents: preventive and corrective strategies against victim behavior." Central to this evaluation was the utilization of a 100-point test designed to measure the knowledge and skills of social pedagogues in addressing issues of victim behavior among adolescents. This test was administered both before and after the training program to evaluate its impact. The test comprised 100 questions with four answer options each, meticulously crafted to assess various aspects of understanding and practical skills of educators related to the behavior of adolescent victims. The test covered areas such as

the identification of victim behavior in adolescents, understanding the psychological foundations of such behavior, intervention, and communication strategies, and methods for creating a supportive and inclusive educational environment. Social pedagogues were allocated one and a half hours to complete the test.

The test was developed as a comprehensive and intricate instrument to accurately reflect the level of qualification of educators in these domains. A score of 100 indicates a high level of knowledge, while a score below 70 suggests areas for improvement. Before the test's integration into the study, the reliability of the 100-point test was meticulously examined. This validation process included a pilot testing phase with a distinct group of social pedagogues who did not participate in the main study. Statistical analysis of the pilot test results ensured the consistency and accuracy of the test questions in measuring the knowledge and skills of educators related to adolescent victim behavior. This validation stage was pivotal in ensuring that the test results served as a reliable indicator of the effectiveness of the training program.

Table 1. Training program outline “modern approaches of social educators with adolescents: preventive and corrective strategies against victim behavior”

Week	Theme	Purpose	Content	Activities
1-2	Understanding adolescent development	Understanding psychological and emotional development of adolescents	Introduction to adolescent psychology, developmental stages, emotional and cognitive changes in adolescence	Lectures, readings, case analysis
3-4	Identification and understanding of victim behavior	Learn to identify signs of victim behavior in adolescents	Characteristics of victim behavior, risk factors, and consequences	Masterclasses, role-playing, guest presentations (psychologists, experienced educators)
5-6	Communication skills and building trust	Develop effective communication strategies to build trust with adolescents	Active listening, empathy, techniques for building trust relationships	Interactive communication exercises, discussions, role-playing
7-8	Intervention strategies for victim behavior	Understanding and applying intervention strategies for victim behavior	Counseling techniques, conflict resolution, and de-escalation strategies	Simulation sessions of counseling, conflict resolution master classes
9-10	Creating an inclusive and supportive school environment	Learn how to contribute to the creation of an inclusive and supportive school culture	Anti-bullying programs, promoting diversity and inclusivity, creating a positive school culture	Group projects for the development of school programs, case discussions
11	Interaction with parents and the community	Understand the role of parents and the community in addressing victim behavior issues	Parental involvement strategies, community resources, multidisciplinary approaches	Role-playing with parent-teachers, community resource mapping
12	Assessment and continuous improvement	Evaluate learning outcomes and plan for continuous professional development	Self-assessment, feedback mechanisms, planning for continuous professional growth	Reflective essays, group feedback sessions, personal growth plan development

2.1. Study design

The study was structured as a quasi-experimental investigation designed to assess the effectiveness of a specialized training program for social pedagogues in addressing issues of victim behavior among adolescents. Both an experimental group (undergoing training) and a control group (not undergoing training) were included in the study, allowing for a comparative analysis of the impact of the training. Participants were social pedagogues from public schools selected through stratified random sampling to ensure a representative composition of educators with varying levels of experience and education. The intervention involved a 12-week educational program titled “modern methods of social pedagogues’ work with adolescents: preventive and corrective strategies against victim behavior.” This program encompassed modules on understanding adolescent psychology, effective intervention strategies, and the creation of a conducive educational environment.

For the implementation phase, a group of social pedagogues from public schools was selected. This group underwent the developed training program. To assess the effectiveness of the program, a “pre-test/post-test” design was employed. The knowledge and skills of the teachers were evaluated before and after the training using a test. A control group of teachers who did not undergo training was also assessed to facilitate a comparative analysis. Participants were randomly divided into two groups: experimental and control, each consisting of 100 social pedagogues. The experimental group participated in the educational program “modern methods of social pedagogues' work with adolescents: preventive and corrective strategies against victim behavior,” while the control group continued to fulfill their standard professional duties without undergoing special training.

To further assess the effectiveness of the training program, an additional comparison was conducted with a group of teachers who received no intervention. This non-intervention group served as a control to determine the impact of the training. The comparative analysis focused on differences in knowledge between the trained group and the control group. The primary instrument for data collection was a 100-point test on the behavior of adolescent victims, administered in both groups before and after the training program. Quantitative pre- and post-test data were analyzed using statistical methods to compare the scores of the experimental and control groups.

2.2. Ethical issues

Adhering to high ethical standards was the cornerstone of this study, ensuring the honesty and credibility of the research while simultaneously safeguarding the interests and well-being of all participants. Key ethical aspects rigorously maintained throughout the study included the following. Each participant received comprehensive information about the purpose of the research, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Informed consent was obtained from all social pedagogues, confirming their voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any time without negative consequences.

Maintaining the confidentiality of participant data was a priority. All collected information was anonymized, and personal data were not referenced in any reports or publications. Access to the data was strictly limited to the research team, and rigorous measures were taken to ensure the secure storage of the data. The design and research methods were reviewed and approved by the institutional review board, ensuring compliance with ethical standards and recommendations for research involving human subjects. Adhering to these ethical principles guaranteed that the study not only provided valuable information but also upheld the highest standards of ethical research practice in the field of social education.

2.3. Research limitations

This study, while comprehensive in its approach to evaluating the training program for social pedagogues, encountered certain limitations that need acknowledgment for a nuanced understanding of the results. One of the primary limitations was the geographic scope of the study. Findings conducted in a specific region may not fully reflect the diverse contexts and challenges faced by social pedagogues in different parts of the country or other countries. Therefore, generalizing the results to a broader population should be approached with caution. Another limitation pertains to the sample size and its selection. Although efforts were made to ensure a representative sample of educators, the relatively small size and the method of stratified random sampling could introduce systematic selection bias, potentially impacting the external validity of the study. Furthermore, the duration of the training program and the subsequent observation period might have been insufficient for observing long-term effects and changes in practice. Longitudinal studies could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the sustained impact of the training. This pertains to the research perspective.

2.4. Participants

The study involved a meticulously selected group of social pedagogues who play a pivotal role in shaping the experiences of adolescents in educational institutions. Participants were drawn from various public secondary schools in the city of Astana, Kazakhstan. The stratified random sampling method was employed in the selection process, ensuring a diverse representation of educators in terms of their experience, education, and demographic characteristics of the schools they serve. This approach aimed to encompass a broad spectrum of perspectives and experiences in the field of social education. In total, 200 educators participated in the study. The average age of participants was 32 years, reflecting a blend of novice and experienced educators. This age range provided a comprehensive view of the applicability and effectiveness of the training program at different stages of professional development. Regarding gender distribution, the group comprised 82% women and 18% men. This ratio reflects the broader demographics in the field of education, where women social pedagogues often constitute a larger proportion.

2.5. Data analysis

In this study, data analysis was meticulously conducted using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS), ensuring a comprehensive and reliable assessment of the results. The analysis encompassed both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a holistic understanding of the impact of the training program. Quantitative data, primarily obtained from the 100-point tests administered before and after the training, were initially summarized using descriptive statistics to comprehend overall trends and score differences. The core of the quantitative analysis involved conducting paired sample t-tests to compare pre- and post-training scores within the experimental group. This approach was crucial in determining whether the training led to a significant improvement in the knowledge and skills of the educators. Additionally, independent sample t-tests compared the post-training results of the experimental group with the control group, assessing the unique effect of the training compared to standard professional development.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

Descriptive statistics are an indispensable tool in research analysis, acting as a guide to elucidate key characteristics of data distributions. This helps ensure an understanding of the nuances of the data set and allows you to draw important conclusions from the analysis. Descriptive statistics of the scores before and after testing are presented in Table 2, providing a quantitative overview of the results in both the experimental and control groups.

For the experimental group, the average score before the test remained unchanged at 43.00, as all participants scored the same. After the training program, post-test results showed a significant increase with a mean of 75.74 and a standard deviation of 3.86, indicating some variability in improvement among participants. The post-test average score was 75.00, with a minimum score of 72 and a maximum score of 86, suggesting that all participants in the experimental group experienced some degree of improvement. In the control group, pre-test results were the same as in the experimental group, with an average score of 43.00 and no deviations. However, post-test results showed a much smaller increase: a mean of 48.73 and a standard deviation of 2.849. The post-test average score was 51.00, but scores varied from a minimum of 39 to a maximum of 51, suggesting that any improvements in the control group were minimal and unrelated to the intervention. The paired-sample t-test for the experimental group was conducted to compare pre-test and post-test results, revealing a significant impact of the training on the knowledge and skills of social educators regarding the behavior of teenage victims. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for pre-test and post-test of social educators on adolescent victim behavior

Group		Pre-test	Post-test
Experimental group	Mean	43.00	75.74
	N	100	100
	Standard deviation	0.000	3.860
	Median	43.00	75.00
	Minimum	43	72
	Maximum	43	86
Control group	Mean	43.00	48.73
	N	100	100
	Standard deviation	0.000	2.849
	Median	43.00	51.00
	Minimum	43	39
	Maximum	43	51

Table 3. Paired samples t-test for experimental and control group

		Pairwise difference						df	Significance (2-tailed)
		Mean value	Standard deviation	Standard error of the mean	95% confidence interval on the difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Pretest-posttest	-32.740	3.860	0.386	-33.506	-31.974	-84.813	99	0.000
Pair 2	Pretest-posttest	-6.010	3.994	0.397	-6.798	-5.221	-15.123	100	0.000

The t-test results for the experimental group (pair 1) indicate a significant increase in average scores from the pre-test to the post-test, with a mean difference of -32.740 points. The standard deviation of differences was 3.860, and the standard error of the mean difference was 0.386. The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranged from -33.506 to -31.974. The t-value of -84.813 with 99 degrees of freedom indicates a highly significant difference in scores before and after the intervention, with a p-value of 0.00. These statistical findings confirm that the training program had a strong and statistically significant impact on the competence of teachers in dealing with the behavior of adolescent victims, with noticeable improvement observed after the training.

In addition to the experimental group, a paired-sample t-test was conducted for the control group to compare the scores before and after testing (pair 2). This analysis aimed to determine whether any significant changes in scores occurred that could be explained by factors other than the training program. For the control group, the results showed a lesser but statistically significant increase in average scores from the pre-test to the post-test, with a mean difference of -6.010 points. The standard deviation of differences was 3.994, and the standard error of the mean difference was 0.397. The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranged from -6.798 to -5.221. The t-value of -15.123 with 100 degrees of freedom indicates a significant difference in scores, with a p-value less than 0.001.

Despite the significant results of the control group, the changes were relatively minor compared to the experimental group. This indicates that, while some improvements may have occurred due to external factors or natural progress in education, the training program brought significantly greater benefits to those who participated in it. Further analysis was conducted using an independent samples t-test to compare the post-testing results of the experimental and control groups. This test was crucial for understanding the differential impact of the training program on the two groups. The results are presented in Table 4.

The assumption of equal variances was tested using Levene's test for equality of variances, yielding an F value of 7.473 with a significance level of 0.007, indicating that the variances were not equal. Despite this, the t-test for equality of means was conducted assuming both equal and unequal variances. In the assumption of equal variances, the t-test for equality of means yielded a t-value of 56.296 with 198 degrees of freedom and a highly significant two-tailed p-value of less than 0.001. The mean difference between the groups was 27.010 points with a standard error of the difference of 0.480. The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranged from 26.064 to 27.956.

When equal variances were not assumed, the t-value remained the same at 56.296, but with adjusted degrees of freedom of 182.181, maintaining the same level of significance. The mean difference and confidence interval remained consistent with the assumption of equal variances, further confirming the substantial impact of the training program. These results demonstrate a significant and statistically meaningful difference in post-test scores between the experimental and control groups, indicating the effectiveness of the training program in enhancing the competency of social educators in dealing with adolescent victim behavior.

Table 4. Independent samples t-test for post-test scores

		Equality of variances Levene's test		t-test for equality of means						
		F	Value	df	Significance (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Mean square error of difference	95% confidence interval on difference		
								Lower	Upper	
Post-test	Assuming equal variances	7.473	0.007	56.296	198	0.000	27.010	0.480	26.064	27.956
	Not assuming equal variances			56.296	182.181	0.000	27.010	0.480	26.063	27.957

3.2. Discussion

The results of this study provide compelling evidence for the effectiveness of the specialized training program in enhancing the abilities of social educators to address issues of adolescent victim behavior. The substantial improvement in post-test scores in the experimental group compared to the control group underscores the value of targeted training. This enhancement aligns with similar research in this field, confirming the trend that specialized training can significantly elevate the competency of educators [27], [28].

Pre-test scores did not reveal significant differences between the groups, establishing a comparable baseline and emphasizing the training itself as a determining factor in post-test outcomes. The substantial increase in post-testing results for the experimental group suggests that the training provided social educators with practical tools and knowledge, enabling them to better handle victim behavior among adolescents. This is particularly noteworthy given the complexities associated with addressing such delicate and multifaceted issues in the school environment [29], [30].

The results of the control group, showing modest improvement, may reflect natural progress in education or the influence of other non-specific professional development activities. However, the stark contrast in the magnitude of improvement with the experimental group indicates the effectiveness of the training program. The alignment of these results with similar studies strengthens the arguments for the broader implementation of such training programs [5], [14]. The data compellingly demonstrate that when social educators possess the necessary skills and knowledge, their ability to positively influence adolescent behavior and alleviate victimization significantly increases [8].

It is crucial to consider the implications of these results for educational policy and practice. The evidence points to the necessity for educational institutions to invest in specialized training programs that enable educators to address the dynamic challenges faced by adolescents. Such investments not only benefit educators but also have far-reaching consequences for the well-being and development of the adolescents they support. Furthermore, this study underscores the need for ongoing research in this field. While the results are promising, further investigations are necessary to enhance training programs and understand their long-term impact on both educators and students [16]. It is also crucial to extend the research to various educational institutions to confirm the generalizability of these findings.

In conclusion, the study provides valuable insights into the role of specialized training in improving the abilities of social educators to address the behavioral issues of adolescent victims. Aligning these results with findings from similar studies complements the growing body of evidence supporting the effectiveness of such initiatives. As the field of social education continues to evolve, it is highly important for such training programs to be considered integral components of educators' professional development [31], [32].

4. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a specialized training program for social educators in addressing victim behavior among adolescents. Utilizing a 100-point test as the assessment method, the research successfully confirmed the positive impact of the training program on educators' ability to understand and respond to such behavior. The study's findings lead to several key conclusions. The substantial improvement in post-test results within the experimental group compared to the control group strongly indicates the effectiveness of the training program. The fact that these educators demonstrated a noticeable enhancement in their understanding and skills, as evidenced by the test results, supports the hypothesis that specialized training in contemporary methodologies can elevate the qualifications of educators in this domain. This conclusion is particularly significant considering the increasing complexity of adolescent behavior and the evolving challenges in the educational environment.

The results of the control group, showing only marginal improvement, suggest that without targeted training, educators may struggle to effectively develop the skills required to address victim behavior among adolescents. This underscores the importance of specialized training compared to general professional development in this specific area of social education. Furthermore, the research findings align with similar studies in this field, affirming the notion that well-structured and purposeful training programs can significantly enhance educators' abilities. This alignment contributes to the growing body of evidence supporting the necessity of such training programs in educational institutions. In conclusion, the study underscores the necessity and effectiveness of specialized training for social educators in dealing with adolescent victim behavior. This contributes to the understanding that targeted educational interventions are essential to equip educators with the necessary tools and skills. These notions urge education policymakers and stakeholders to consider the integration of such training programs into the system of teachers' professional development, thereby enhancing the overall educational experience and well-being of adolescents.

REFERENCES

- [1] F.-Y. Hong and K.-T. Cheng. "Correlation between university students' online trolling behavior and online trolling victimization forms, current conditions, and personality traits," *Telematics and Informatics*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 397–405, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.tele.2017.12.016.
- [2] E. Vera *et al.*, "Promoting upstanding behavior in youth: a proposed model," *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 1020–1049, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1177/0272431618798514.
- [3] S. Fitriani and L. Qodariah, "A child-friendly school: how the school implements the model," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 273–284, 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v10i1.20765.
- [4] A. R. Drozdikova-Zaripova, N. Y. Kostyunina, and N. N. Kalatskaya, "Prevention of student youth's victim behavior," *Review of European Studies*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 88–92, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.5539/res.v7n4p88.
- [5] M. Murzagulova, K. Atemova, L. Suleimenova, N. Arynova, and B. Batyrbaeva, "Training of future social educators on prevention of the propensity of adolescents to victim behavior," *The Journal of Psychology & Sociology*, vol. 72, no. 3, pp. 43–52, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.26577/JES.2022.v72.i3.04.
- [6] C. Potard, V. Kubiszewski, C. Combes, A. Henry, R. Pochon, and A. Roy, "How adolescents cope with bullying at school: exploring differences between pure victim and bully-victim roles," *International Journal of Bullying Prevention*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 144–159, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s42380-021-00095-6.
- [7] D. M. Radulović and Z. Ilić, "Children and young with antisocial propensity: theoretical models for identification and social importance of prevention of antisocial behaviour," *Sociologija*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 497–517, 2018, doi: 10.2298/SOC1802497R.
- [8] T. G. Bobchenko, "Personal traits of adolescents prone to victim behavior on the internet," *Vestnik Altaiskogo Gosudarstvennogo Pedagogiceskogo Universiteta*, vol. 55, pp. 59–65, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.37386/2413-4481-2023-2-59-65.
- [9] Y. Han, J. Ma, E. Bang, and J. Song, "Dynamics of bullies and victims among Korean youth: a propensity score stratification analysis," *Children and Youth Services Review*, vol. 98, pp. 252–260, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2018.12.029.
- [10] C. Maes, J. van Ouytsel, and L. Vandenbosch, "Victim blaming and non-consensual forwarding of sexts among late adolescents and young adults," *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 1767–1783, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10508-023-02537-2.
- [11] V. L. Banyard, K. M. Edwards, A. J. Rizzo, E. F. Rothman, P. Greenberg, and M. C. Kearns, "Improving social norms and actions to prevent sexual and intimate partner violence: a pilot study of the impact of green dot community on youth," *Journal of Prevention and Health Promotion*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 183–211, 2020, doi: 10.1177/2632077020966571.
- [12] T. G. Bobchenko, "Value orientation of older adolescents who are prone to victim behavior," *Vestnik Altaiskogo Gosudarstvennogo Pedagogiceskogo Universiteta*, vol. 51, pp. 62–68, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.37386/2413-4481-2022-2-62-68.
- [13] J. R. Baldwin *et al.*, "Adolescent victimization and self-injurious thoughts and behaviors: a genetically sensitive cohort study," *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, vol. 58, no. 5, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jaac.2018.07.903.
- [14] J. Z. Torybayeva, "The future teacher-psychologist training for the prevention of suicidal behavior in adolescents," *BULLETIN Series Psychology*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 189–199, 2021, doi: 10.51889/2021-3.1728-7847.22.

- [15] A. T. Tangwe, "School Violence and Open Spaces for Learning in Cameroon," *American Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 85–98, 2022, doi: 10.12691/education-10-2-3.
- [16] O. O. Bantysheva, "Adolescents' propensity towards some forms of victim behaviour in accordance with their future profession: empirical study," *Scientific notes of Taurida National V.I. Vernadsky University, series Psychology*, vol. 4, pp. 171–176, 2020, doi: 10.32838/2709-3093/2020.4/26.
- [17] Y. Pidvalna, "Socio-psychological factors as the basis for formation of victim and buller behavior," *Academic Notes. Series: Pedagogical Science*, vol. 1, no. 185, pp. 143–146, 2020, doi: 10.36550/2415-7988-2019-1-185-143-146.
- [18] D. S. Everstine and L. Everstine, "The boy victim," in *Sexual Trauma in Children and Adolescents*, New York, NY: Routledge, 2019, pp. 129–150, doi: 10.4324/9781315784205-6.
- [19] O. G. Yaparova and A. A. Abolevich, "Socio-psychological predictors of victim behaviour in adolescents," *Comprehensive Child Studies*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 272–284, 2019, doi: 10.33910/2687-0223-2019-1-4-272-284.
- [20] G. Sitota and B. Tefera, "Family cohesion and disruptive behavior among school adolescents: the mediating role of self-regulation," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 9–17, 2024, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v13i1.24969.
- [21] T. Kalyazina, "Psychological characteristics of intellectually gifted adolescents propensity to victimization behavior," *Bulletin of Postgraduate Education (Series «Social and behavioural sciences»)*, vol. 35, pp. 78–91, 2018, doi: 10.32405/2522-9931-2018-6(35)-78-91.
- [22] J. Oh, E. kim, and H. Yoon, "Effects of parental conflict and teacher behavior on adolescents' psychological adaptation and bully/victim status," *Journal of School Social Work*, vol. 41, pp. 221–246, 2018, doi: 10.20993/jssw.41.10.
- [23] W. DeCamp, H. Zaykowski, and B. Lunn, "Victim-offender trajectories: explaining propensity differences from childhood to adulthood through risk and protective factors," *British Journal of Criminology*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 667–688, 2018, doi: 10.1093/bjc/azx052.
- [24] A. A. Grigoryeva and L. E. Usova, "Relationship between propensity to victim behavior and the risks of substance use in adolescents," *Psychology and Law*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 211–223, 2020, doi: 10.17759/psylaw.2020100314.
- [25] M. Jia and A. Y. Mikami, "Peer preference and friendship quantity in children with externalizing behavior: distinct influences on bully status and victim status," *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 957–969, 2015, doi: 10.1007/s10802-014-9956-8.
- [26] S. Ilma, M. H. I. Al-Muhdhar, F. Rohman, and M. S. Sari, "Promoting students' metacognitive awareness and cognitive learning outcomes in science education," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 20–30, 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v11i1.22083.
- [27] M. Kushner and A. A. Fagan, "The effects of victimization on offending: an examination of general strain theory, criminal propensity, risk, protection, and resilience," *Victims and Offenders*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 1009–1029, 2023, doi: 10.1080/15564886.2022.2077495.
- [28] A. Yendell, V. Clemens, J. Schuler, and O. Decker, "What makes a violent mind? the interplay of parental rearing, dark triad personality traits and propensity for violence in a sample of German adolescents," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 17, no. 6, p. e0268992, 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0268992.
- [29] E. M. Rothe, "Inside the mind of the adolescent school shooter: contributing factors and prevention," *World Social Psychiatry*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 85–93, 2022, doi: 10.4103/wsp.wsp_18_22.
- [30] L. Kayumova, V. Zakirova, and M. Aleksandrovich, "Social risks in the youth environment: the experience of Russia and Poland," in *ARPHA Proceedings*, Feb. 2022, pp. 791–810, doi: 10.3897/ap.5.e0791.
- [31] L. Almond, M. A. McManus, and H. Chatterton, "Internet facilitated rape: a multivariate model of offense behavior," *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, vol. 35, no. 21–22, pp. 4979–5004, 2020, doi: 10.1177/0886260517718187.
- [32] R. Miranda, X. Oriol, and A. Amutio, "Risk and protective factors at school: reducing bullies and promoting positive bystanders' behaviors in adolescence," *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 106–115, 2019, doi: 10.1111/sjop.12513.

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